

EDUCATION IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBALIZATION ISSUES**Muhammadjonova Ogiloy**

2nd year student of FarSU.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11912776>

Abstract. This article provides information about globalization and the place and role of this process in the issue of education and training, as well as the advantages of the process of globalization and how important this process is in the issue of education and training.

Key words: globalization, factor, region, regions, development, objective, development

ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ В УСЛОВИЯХ ПРОБЛЕМ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена информация о глобализации, месте и роли этого процесса в вопросе образования и обучения, а также о преимуществах процесса глобализации и о том, насколько важен этот процесс в вопросе образования и обучения.

Ключевые слова: глобализация, фактор, регион, регионы, развитие, цель, развитие.

INTRODUCTION

When talking about the main factor and reason why the process of globalization is entering our lives more and more quickly and deeply, it should be objectively recognized that today the development and prosperity of any country is closely related not only to its near and far neighbors, but also to other regions and regions on a global scale. It is not difficult to understand that the exclusion of any country from this process will not lead to positive results. In this sense, globalization means, first of all, an incomparable acceleration of the pace of life.

The term "Globalization" was first used by the American scientist T. Levitt in his article published in "Harvard Business Review" in 1983. T. Levitt called the processes of integration of various product markets produced by large multinational corporations as "globalization". In this definition, attention is paid to the economic aspects of the globalization process. In his time, the French philosopher R. Descartes wrote: "Clarify the meaning of concepts and this will save half of humanity from going astray." In this sense, at first we will try to explain the terminological meaning of the concept of "globalization". This word can be defined as follows: Globalization is an objective process of development of the world economy, which has many positive features: these are mainly the interaction of the economies of different countries, the attraction of foreign investments, science - it is confirmed by the acceleration of the exchange of science and technology achievements and assistance to the scientific and technical development of the countries.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Globalization is the process of worldwide economic political, cultural integration and unification. The main goal of the reforms carried out in the field of education is to bring up a well-rounded person with a free and independent opinion and a qualified specialist¹. Let's shed some light on the concept of communication when studying the process of formation of mental and spiritual image of students in the conditions of globalization. A transaction is an information process. Information goes in two directions: from the subject of management (the teacher) to the object of management (students) and vice versa - from the object to the subject. By the beginning of the 21st century, the interaction between the countries of the world has intensified to such an extent that it is possible to say with full confidence that there is not a single country that is completely protected from this process. Even the countries that are trying to distance themselves from international organizations and do not want to join them are not excluded from this process.

Globalization is such a process that the countries that say they stay away from it are more affected by it. Such involuntary influence often leads to negative consequences. Globalization, which is rapidly developing today, is acquiring a new meaning in the spirituality of every state, people, nation, or humanity. In the development of society, "just like every social phenomenon has its positive and negative side, the process of globalization is no exception.

But we should not forget that together with such achievements, globalization poses a moral threat to the national idea, ideology, faith and heritage of some peoples. The era of globalization has brought significant changes in the way we live, work and communicate with each other. As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, people are increasingly turning to spirituality as a means of inner peace, purpose, and self-fulfillment. In this article, we discuss the main aspects of spiritual education in the context of globalization we will also consider the need for a holistic approach that combines traditional wisdom with modern knowledge. will be in mind. The main priorities of modern youth are interest in literature and art, higher education, ability to choose moral values, professional skills and competence, sensitivity to nature and people, development of professional outlook. That is, the sign of a cultured person for young people is his comprehensive development.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A great achievement of globalization is the development of the world information network - the Internet. The Internet is recognized as the most popular source of information. Young people are especially impressionable and quickly adopt various technical innovations. For them, using the Internet is a sign of "symbolic consumption" and "convenience of life" like a private car or travel.

In 65% of cases, they turn to the Internet not to meet professional needs, but to fill free time. Today, globalization is actively transforming the world, covering all spheres of human life - economy, law, culture, language, education, spiritual and moral development. Three aspects of globalization can be distinguished: first, adherence to generally recognized norms of behavior, commitment to common cultural values and single life principles, striving to universalize everything; secondly, the integration and growing interconnectedness of individual forms of social life; thirdly, it is a social aspect that depends on the change of life strategies and social relations of individuals. When it comes to human education, there are different types of education, just as the role and tasks of a person in society are different. Each education method has its own direction and methods. In the current era of globalization and spiritual-educational struggles, spiritual-educational education is one of the most important and relevant forms of education. First of all, in order to achieve the effectiveness of spiritual and educational education, the level of knowledge and thinking ability of the educated person also play a decisive role.

In our country's youth policy, the Law "On Education", the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Policy Regarding Youth", the in-depth education of young people, the development of their intellectual potential, the realization of their abilities all possibilities are opened for its exit. This shows that the youth of our country have all the opportunities to absorb spiritual and educational education and to realize the goal set in the idea of national independence.

Another goal of spiritual and educational education is to abandon the usual, traditional way of thinking and move to a new, advanced way of thinking. Spiritual and educational education is a continuous process, which is separated from education. it will not happen, because education cannot be realized without spiritual and educational education, and spiritual and educational education cannot be realized without education. In our opinion, the following tasks should be performed in order to combine spiritual and educational education with continuous education:

- 1) to create a new pedagogical and psychological program of inculcating national independence ideology in the educational system of children and students of all ages in accordance with their age characteristics;

- 2) to include in the national personnel training program a direction on continuous formation of the national idea and ideology of national independence in the minds of individual pupils and students;

- 3) inculcate the main ideas of the national independence ideology in the state educational standards, textbooks and manuals, regardless of the field;

- 4) raising spiritual and educational education in schools, lyceums, colleges and institutes, universities to a high, primary level;

5) introduction of training courses for all specialties in order to deepen the spiritual and educational knowledge of pedagogical personnel;

6) inculcate the idea of national independence in the minds of young people at every stage of education.

CONCLUSION

Today's globalization processes change the ideological and ideological image of the world and demand a new way of thinking. Therefore, in Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the socialization of education and the harmonization of science with the requirements of the time. In addition to educating students and youth as personnel who have deep knowledge of certain specialties and professions, who can show self-sacrifice for the benefit of the Motherland and the people, who deeply understand the essence and value of our independence, and it is his sacred duty to protect it from any danger. It is one of the most important tasks to raise people who know that.

REFERENCES

1. Sorokin V. Globalization and civilization: an analytical approach. M.: Mysl. 2010. - S. 261
2. Afanasev K. Political science. M.: Knowledge. 2009, -S.109
3. Khasanov E. The theory of national spirituality. T.: Spirituality, 2014.-B.8
4. Doniyorov B. Ways to attract young students to spiritual and educational work. T.: Spirituality, 2011.-B.5-6
5. Khasanov I. Spiritual science. T.: East, 2016.-B.23
6. Shavkat Mirziyoev expressed his opinion about the painful points of our society // darakchi.uz URL: <https://darakchi.uz/oz/29070>
7. Uzbekistan's experience in the fight against extremism and terrorism
8. Omirzakov, R. (2023). SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS AND ITS ROLE IN THE STATE POLICY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE FIELD OF ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION. International Journal Of Law And Criminology, 3(07), 89-93.
9. Egamberdiyev, O. A. O., Turdaliyev, A. Y. O., & Makhamadjonov, J. Z. O. (2021). Pedagogical bases of formation of professional competence. Science and Education, 2(11), 985-991.
10. Zarnigor, R. A. Q., Egamberdiyev, O. A. O. G. L., & Sotvoldiyeva, O. M. R. Q. (2021). Pedagogical competence: theoretical and practical analysis. Science and Education, 2(9), 309-314.

11. Egamberdiyev, O. A. O., Sotvoldiyeva, O. M. Q., & Turdaliyev, A. Y. O. (2021). PROBLEM WAYS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(10), 535-542.
12. Yusufovich, A. A. (2020). ISSUES OF FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE, WHICH IS AN INTEGRAL PART OF PROFESSIONAL-PEDAGOGICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 8(7).
13. Tojimamatov, J., & Egamberdiyev, O. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF A PERSON.